

Composition and Stability of U(VI)-7-Bromo-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid Chelate

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Uranium (VI) forms in aqueous medium, an orange red complex with 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid with the maximum absorbance at 350 $m\mu$, stable in the pH range 3-7. The composition of the complex as established by three different methods spectrophotometrically is $U(VI)R_2$ (where R stands for 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid). The stability constant calculated by the methods of Banerji and Dey and the Mole-ratio method was found to be $\log K = 9.04 \pm 0.05$ at 30° and the free energy of formation was found to be -12.57 ± 0.07 Kcal/mole at 30°. A constant ionic strength of 0.1M was maintained in all experiments.

Albert and Magrath¹ found that many metal ions did not form a precipitate but changed colour with 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid. 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid also shows colour changes with a number of metal ions. In these investigations, 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid has been prepared by the method used by Banerji and Srivastava² and Tio Hsu Chang³. The complex formation between this reagent and Uranyl nitrate is instantaneous. The nature and composition of the complex formed has been studied spectrophotometrically using Job's method of Continuous Variation⁴, Mole-ratio method⁵ and Slope-ratio method⁶. The stability constants and free energy of formation have also been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard solution of Uranium was prepared by dissolving Uranyl nitrate (A.R.) in double distilled water. A purified sample of 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid was used for the preparation of stock solution in double distilled water. Absorbance measurements were made on a Hilger-UVISPEC spectrophotometer (Model H 700-380) fitted with a thermostated jacket using one cm. effective light path. Measurements of pH were made at 30° and the chelate formed was studied under optimum conditions.

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RESULTS

Effect of the pH on the chelate : Solutions containing the same concentration ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$) of the reagent and Uranyl nitrate were prepared at different pH and the absorbance at various wavelengths were taken. The complex showed λ_{\max} . at $350 m\mu$ in the pH range 3-7 (fig. 1).

FIG.— 1
Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the absorption-maxima of the chelate. ($c = 2 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 1$).

Nature of the complex formed : To find out the nature of the complex formed, Vosburgh and Cooper's method⁷ was adopted. Mixtures containing various proportions of Uranyl nitrate and the reagent (1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4) were prepared and after adjusting the pH of the mixtures at 6.6 ± 0.1 , the absorbance measurements were made. The results as graphically represented in fig. 2, will show that only one complex is formed with a λ_{\max} in the region of $350 m\mu$.

Composition of the complex : As has been said before, the composition of the complex was studied by three different methods.

Job's method : Job's method of continuous variation⁴, has been adopted for determining the composition of the complex. The absorbance of the mixture and the chelating agent were measured at two different wavelengths of $350 m\mu$ and $360 m\mu$, using both equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions at a pH 6.6. As will be seen from the same, U(VI) ion reacts with the ligand, forming the chelate with metal : chelating agent ratio of 1 : 2.

Mole-ratio method : In the determination of the composition by Mole-ratio method⁵, a series of solutions were prepared with the mole-ratios of the metal ion : reagent varying from 0.05 : 1 to 8 : 1. The results of the studies at a pH 6.6 ± 0.1 and $350 m\mu$ when plotted shows a break at a ratio of metal : reagent 1 : 2 indicating that the composition of the complex is 1 : 2.

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Slope-ratio Method: In the determination of composition by Slope-ratio method⁶, the final concentration of the variable component was varied from $4.8 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $4.8 \times 10^{-5} M$ in presence of an excess of $1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ of the constant component.

FIG. 2

Fig. 2. Absorption-spectra of the mixtures of Uranyl nitrate and 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid at $pH\ 6.6 \pm 0.1$.

Curve 1, Reagent alone (c')	$= 2 \times 10^{-4} M$.	
Curve 2,	$c = 2 \times 10^{-4} M$;	$p = 1$.
Curve 3,	$c = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$;	$p = 2$.
Curve 4,	$c = 6.66 \times 10^{-5} M$;	$p = 3$.
Curve 4,	$c = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$;	$p = 4$.

Evaluation of Stability Constant: For the purpose of the determination of the stability constant of the complex, calculations have been made by the method used by Banerji and Dey⁸ and the Mole-ratio method⁵. The values of $\log K$ obtained were 9.04 ± 0.05 at 30° . The free energy of formation ΔF calculated comes out to be -12.57 ± 0.07 Kcal/mole at 30° .

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